

Career Development and Information Counselling: Individual Decision-Making Perspective

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Abstract

A counsellor cannot do an effective and transformative counselling without proper information either from the client, environment, modern technologies, or every other means through which information is gotten. In this case, good-quality information counselling has been considered as the hallmark of career development. Often, this good-quality information seems to be lacking in the counselling process, and this usually affects the individual or client's decision-making. This occurs when the individual is confused or overclouded with the particular profession to embark upon, or when he or she is faced with varieties of alternatives. This work, therefore, seeks to critically examine the problem of decision-making that seems to have been persistently occurring among persons, and which has made career development as well as the occupational destination of some clients difficult or uncertain. The work rightly discovers that many people, oftentimes, find it difficult to take decision regarding their career, and this seems to be posing a problem in career development. It suggests that for this fear of uncertainty in decision making to be solved, a counsellor should always try to build confidence in the client. Also, there should be a mutual understanding and proper communication between the client and the counsellor for better career development, and this, the researcher believe, will lead to progressive occupational destination.

Key words: Career, Career development, information, counselling, information counselling, and decision-making perspective

Introduction

There is no doubt of the fact that good-quality information counselling remains the hallmark of career development. Often, this good-quality information seems to be lacking in the counselling process. With this, some individuals or career seekers find it difficult to adjust themselves, or embark on one profession or the other. As a result, fear of uncertainty becomes a problem, or often leads to suspicion and lack of mutual understanding between the client and the counsellor. This study, therefore, seeks to critically examine the relational problem that seems to have persistently occurring between the client and the counselor, and which has made career

development as well as the occupational destination of some clients difficult. The paper sets out to examine the relational perspective of career development and information counselling. To this end, this study begins with the clarification of terms used in this paper. It will briefly give the historical structure and meaning of career development and information counselling. Other parts of the work are career development and decision-making, and conclusion of the work.

Clarification of Terms

Before delving into the topic proper, there is need to clarify some of the terms employ in this study. This will help to curb the problem of ambiguity and cloudiness in the meaning of some the terms used in this paper. The terms to be clarified here include: career, career development, and information counselling.

Information Counselling

There are various definitions of information counselling given by different scholars. Information counselling is a global approach to individual under all aspects of their personal professional and social life. It consists of providing information, counselling and guidance service with a view to supporting each and every person in any stage of their life. Individual develop their own career through decision-making.

Collection of information, with regard to counselling, has some known methods or techniques like psychological tests, questionnaires, and inventories of interest, preference aptitudes, attitudes and values. Some of the techniques like tests, questionnaires or inventories play a very significant role in gathering information about the personality in question, aptitude with regard to intellectual, verbal, numerical, reasoning, reaction, speed, special talents and so on of the clients. Other information include: interest and special needs, values and attitudes; assessment of academic such as learning skills and methods; interpersonal relations; self-image, decision-making; career development like training for decision making; and special categories of population. In information counselling, the client is expected to avails the counselor the necessary information for better assessment.

Hence, good quality information is necessary for good career development. It needs to include information on education, training opportunities on occupation and their characteristics, then on labour market supply and demand. It also needs to include information on the occupational implications on educational decisions, and on the learning pathways that lead to particular occupational destinations. Further, it needs to include information on how these opportunities relate to the characteristics and preferences of individual, so that individuals can identify opportunities appropriate to them. Information and communication technologies need to be harnessed creatively in order to improve the quality, interconnectedness, and accessibility of such information towards appropriate career development. Since we have examined the concept

information, it is important also to explore the concept of career and career development, and its emergence in career guidance or counselling.

Career Development

The term *career* has been conceived, or defined in serious ways by different scholars within and outside counselling domain. For example, it has been used in relation to a range of aspects of an individual's life, learning and work. In this way, it refers to the working aspects of an individual's life e.g. as in career man or woman. When it is used to describe an occupation or a profession that usually involved special training or formal education, it is considered to be a person's lifework. In this approach, it is seen as sequence of related jobs usually pursued within a single industry or sector e.g. "a career in education" or "a career in the building trade". Many scholars have also offered their individual definitions of career development. These various definitions of career show that career development has no consensus or generally accepted definition. No wonder Schreuder and Coetzee (2006) explained that a career consists of different stages and the individual is confronted with different issues during each of these stages.

On the other hand, *Career Development* is a lifelong process of managing, learning and working. According to Baer, Flexer, Luft and Simmons (2008) an individual's career development is a lifetime process that encompasses the growth and change process of childhood, the formal career education at school, and the maturational processes that continue throughout a person's working adulthood and into retirement. Herr (1999) stated that the use of the term career development as descriptive of the both the factor and processes influencing individual career behavior and as synonymous with intervention in career behavior is relatively recent. As professional vocabulary evolves across time, so do the form and substance of career interventions and those to whom they are directed. In line with this, Niles & Harris-Bowlsbey (2002) conceived career development as the lifelong psychological and behavioural processes as well as contextual influences shaping one's career over the life span. As such, career development involves the person's creation of a career pattern, decision-making style, integration of life roles, values expression, and life-role self concepts. McKay (2017) defined career development as the process that forms a person's work identity. Stating further, he said that career development is a significant part of human development and span over the individual's entire lifetime, beginning when the individual first becomes aware of how people make a living.

Emergence of Career Development

The emergence of career development depends of the prevailing needs of different individuals, societies and cultures. In Herr's account, career development as used in the title of the National Career Development Association, had increasingly come, at the end of the twentieth century, to describe both the constellation of psychological, sociological, educational, physical, economic, and chance factors that combine to shape individual career behavior over the life span, and the interventions or practices that are used to enhance a person's career development or to enable that person to make more effective career decisions. Herr made us to understand that

inherent in the career development are two sets of theories, or conceptual categories, one that explains the development of career behaviour across the life span and the other that describes how career behavior is changed by particular interventions. According to him, the contemporary use of the term *career development* is important to establish that terms like professions, evolved.

Herr states that *the term career* was rarely used before the 1960s, while the terms *development* was rarely used before the 1950s. So combining the two terms, they intended until the late 1960s to be described as vocational development or vocational psychology, not career development. Herr states that based on the historical references to career development practice are more like to use the terms like vocational guidance or counseling, or career guidance or counseling, rather than career development practice, but all of these flow from the same roots. Important question remains: What is the root from where all these related terms flow?

The fact remains that one cannot talk of career development without making reference to the period of industrial revolution in Europe and America, and other prevailing waves of world's civilizations. No wonder Capuzzi and Stauffer (2012) asserted that all career and vocational theories develop within a historical context. Therefore, examining the historical roots and development of different vocational theories provides a basis for understanding their lineage, a context for how they develop over time, and a sense of their connection to U.S. history and prevailing culture. With this, they went further to examine major influences on U.S. vocational counselling theory and practice in an effort to present a contextual portrait of the field and its growth. This portrait includes key figures, legislation, institutions and professional organizations, licensure and accreditation, and world events. In line with this contextual influences that have shaped the history of vocational counseling, Gysbers, Heppner, Johnston, and Neville(2003) identified five tenets that influenced the development of career counselling research, theory, and practice in the United States: (1) individualism and autonomy, (2) affluence, (3) an open structure of opportunity based on assumptions of merit, (4) work as the central role in people's lives, and (5) the logical, linear, and progressive development of work and career (pp. 53–57). These tenets, according to them, reflect the U.S. mainstream culture's assumptions that (a) the individual is the primary unit of focus, (b) individuals make career choices (vs. family or collectivist decision making), (c) individuation represents psychological progress and development, (d) volition and unconstrained choices guide occupational decisions, (e) the world of work operates as a meritocracy free from biases (e.g., racism, sexism), and (f) work is the most important aspect of people's lives. These assumptions rely on a static work culture and environment that no longer exists, even for those who once enjoyed its benefits, and completely ignore the realities of many others (Gysbers, Heppner, Johnston, & Neville, 2003).

Aubrey (1977), in Capuzzi and Stauffer (2012), gave historical antecedence of career development. According to him, the mid- and late 1800s were marked by a devastating civil war, periods of economic depression, the closing of the American frontier, unbridled growth of large metropolitan areas, large waves of uneducated and unskilled immigrants, a war with the fading

Spanish empire, unchecked expansion of family fortunes through business and industry, abrupt and unforeseen modes of communication and transportation, legal freeing of millions of former slaves without concomitant economic and social autonomy, the challenge to established religions by social and biological Darwinism, the rapid spread of compulsory school attendance laws, concentration of job opportunities in large cities, growth of state and federal government to cope with the earlier enlargement of corporate and industrial complexes, the struggle of women for basic human rights, and, the increased exploitation of many segments of the United States population by unscrupulous hucksters and entrepreneurs.

As seen we can, emergence of career development in the United States were marked by large-scale economic and demographic changes that came after the Industrial Revolution. The second major immigration wave in the United States was marked by mass movement into the cities from rural areas in the United States and abroad and included people from many nations, members of ethnic minority groups, farmers, Southerners, and youth(Pope,2000). This immigration was accompanied by xenophobic social movements as well as restrictive immigration legislation after World War I, and continued through the Depression and World War II (McLemore et al., 2001). There was little sympathy for the plight of new arrivals, many of whom found work only in the most abysmal conditions. Labor unions emerged in the middle of the 1800s and grew in strength to become important political forces by the turn of the century (DeBell, 2001).

From the above exploration of emergence of career development, three factors remain outstanding. They include: urbanization, industrialization and immigration. These are factors that propelled individuals as they move on with, and in search of a better career. With regard to theories of career development, Savikas (2009) warned that current career development theories and techniques face a crisis in that their fundamental assumption of predictability based on stability and stages is debatable and, more importantly, may no longer be functional.

Further, models of career development have identified age ranges in which individuals typically encounter the tasks associated with each stage of career development. Moreover, the models appear to have assumed that individuals pursue a continuous linear career within one occupation, in perhaps one or two organizations, and without major disruptions or redirections.

However, Greenhaus (2001) cautioned that despite many of the outmoded assumptions of age-related theories of development, it is important not to disregard the effects of age and psychological life tasks associated with that. Flexer, Baer, Luft and Simmons (2008) stated that although these four stages are specific to employment, a broad definition of career development incorporates all life areas. Flexer et al (2008) proposed that there should be an inclusion of the influences from other life roles and responsibilities that ultimately lead to a satisfactory quality of life. They conclude that the four stages support a comprehensive view of career development and transition planning. While there are four discrete stages of development, they do not

necessarily only take place once in an individual's life, but could take place on numerous occasions through career changes, such as changing jobs (Flexer et al., 2008).

According to Stead and Watson (1999), the following developmental tasks are still appropriate during each life stage, although the nature of these tasks will change. They involve gaining appropriate self-information, displaying effective decision making skills, gaining appropriate career information, integrating self and career information and planning a career. However, it is suggested that these stages are now happening more and more frequently. Greenhaus (2001) therefore proposed that the career of the 21st century is not measured by chronological age and life stages, but by continuous learning and identity changes. Greenhaus proposed that this is more of an accurate view rather than thinking of a career that constitutes a series of developmental stages, as we might expect from the work of the 20th century.

Career development and Individual Career Decision Making

Another thing to discuss here is career development with regard to individual career decision-making process. It determines earnings, job security, friends, and acquaintances, the amount of leisure time and residence. Greenhaus (2003) explained that much career-related behaviours explicitly or implicitly involve a career decision: to pursue a particular job, to increase or decrease involvement in work, or to change occupational fields. Although each situation is different, they all involve action in the face of alternatives. Career decision is made many times throughout ones career.

Also, the nature of schooling, family socio-economic background, influence of family members and close friends, and the expectations that evolve from these interactions are seen as the prime determinants of occupational choice, level of attainment and what prompts a person to make a career change or career path re-alignment. With all these factors involved in career decision making the young adult should not delay making a career decision. Feldman (2002) cautioned the longer youth are undecided about their career goals, the longer they may stay underemployed. The longer they stay underemployed the less desirable they may be as candidates for higher skilled jobs.

Career indecision is considered to be challenging for youth in the school-to-work-transition as youth generally have not had enough work experience to develop their career identity. The young adult's self concept undergoes turbulent times as they are faced with multiple demands to perform and become an independent citizen. The young adult should get into the mindset of becoming proactive with their career decisions. Greenhaus (2003) pointed out that due to the emergence of shorter and more frequent career cycles, an individual will be required to make a greater number of significant career decisions over the course of their lives. Organizations can assist youth preparing to enter the world of work in understanding the decisions that need to be made, and provide those individuals with the skills necessary to make well informed decisions. It therefore seems reasonable to suggest that organizations should not ignore the fact

that individuals need to develop and maintain their employability. They should embrace the process as a strategy for employee empowerment and motivation development.

Conclusion

As said above, the hallmark of career counselling, vocational guidance or counselling, or career development, is to help the individual to take appropriate decision in life regarding his or her career; assessment of the individual in job; identifying the capabilities of the individual; psychological assessment, and other related issues. In this work, effort is made to critically examine the impact of career development and information counselling on individual decision-making. The fact remains that career development cannot thrive without proper information. A client who seeks the assistance from a counselor should be free with the counselor. We should bear in mind that human development and growth is taking place in a world filled with interest, where the global market is overwhelmed by social, political, and technological changes and economic diversification within the flow of globalization. These tendencies are linked to changes in the labour market structure, and are accompanied by readjustment in the social arrangement. Therefore, career development and information counselling is very vital for one to achieve his or her aim in this contemporary and dynamic world.

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